

A STUDY ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR IN HOSPITALS

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Abstract

Organizations are compelled to continuously modernize in response to global economic realities. They may have to address the difficulty of limiting operating costs by reducing the number of employees. The corporation then assigns additional work to the employees that were retained. Employers require employees who will go above and beyond the call of duty. These employees routinely go above and above the requirements of their jobs, which increases the overall effectiveness of the organization. The organization should focus its retention efforts on these employees in order to retain and promote effective and successful workplace functioning. The goal of this research is to investigate how generally perceived organizational commitment as well as influence organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in hospitals. To provide supporting data, a survey and a study of the literature were conducted.

Keywords: Organization, Hospital, OCB, Perceived Organizational support, Organizational Commitment, Cognitive Commitment

1. INTRODUCTION

Bateman and Organ's research was particularly concerned with highlighting organizational citizenship behavior (1983). Individual employees' unrestricted actions outside of their allocated roles are referred to as organizational citizenship behaviors. Although these behaviors may improve an organization's efficiency and performance, the organization's reward structure does not explicitly reward them (Organ, 1988). Being willing to compromise when things become rough at work, operating in accordance with organizational standards, rules, and guiding principles, and taking a significant interest in organizational development that leads to organizational success are all examples of organizational citizenship behavior (Katz and Kahn, 1966). The goal of this research is to look into how nursing staff behave in terms of organizational citizenship. In particular, private hospitals is influenced by perceived organizational support and organizational commitment. Administrators can better grasp the characteristics of organizational citizenship behavior by using the study's findings as a guide as they develop strategies for fostering it.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Perceived Organizational Support

Eisenburger, Huntington, Hutchison, and Sowa claim that (1986), Employees' view of how much their efforts are treasured and how much the firm bothers about their health is known as organizational commitment. Furthermore, the authors contended that perceived organizational support influenced employees' expectations in a variety of situations.

2.2 Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment, according to Porter (1968), is characterised as an employee's readiness to go above and beyond for the organisation, acceptance of its core values, standards, and guiding principles, and a strong desire to stay with the company. The three most often studied forms of organizational contribution, according to Meyer and Allen (1991), are Emotional contribution, continuous contribution, and perspective contribution.

2.3 Appropriate connection

According to Hartmann and Bambacas, Affective commitment, defined as an emotion of fondness as well as sentiments of loyalty to the organization, has been connected to work experiences, personality traits, and organizational structures (2000).

Continuance Commitment, Meyers and co. (1993) define as follows: being aware of the expenses connected with leaving the company or job. Workers who are adamant about sticking with the organisation do so because they recognise the importance, risks, and limited possibilities of quitting.

2.4 Normative Commitment

Workers with a high level of loyalty feel ethically bound to stay with the business or employment, and conscientiousness is defined as the sense of responsibility to keep working. (Meyer et.al., 1993). The extent to which a person internalises an organization's vision, goals, objectives, principles, values, and missions demonstrates their normative commitment to it.

2.5 Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organ (1988) described organizational citizenship behaviors as highly valued workplace actions made by employees that are optional, not clearly or directly indicated in job descriptions or official remuneration plans, and that In general, they help the firm run more smoothly and efficiently.

Organizational citizenship behaviors are desirable and helpful from an organizational standpoint, according to Moorman and Blakely (1995), but managers find it difficult to coerce them through official contracts and incentives because they are voluntary. Organ (1990)

Identified five distinct organizational citizenship behaviors:

- Employees that exhibit sportsmanship do not criticise but instead are positive and encouraging. Employees value their co-workers and treat them with respect, according to courtesy.
- Employees that are conscientious go above and above the minimal required levels of performance.
- Employees who are altruistic aid others who work with them.

Hypotheses development

Organizational Citizenship Behaviour and Perceived Organizational Support

There is contradictory evidence relating perceived organizational support and civic behavior. According to a study by Eisenberger et al., employees like to personify organisations, establishing a general attitude based on how the entity appreciates their efforts and is concerned about their health. (1990). They also discovered a correlation between observed workplace support and company's reform ideas.. Wayne, Shore, and Liden (1997) discovered a link a difference in psychological empowerment and supervisors' evaluations of employees' company as well as individual civic behavior.

According to Graham (1991), there is a positive feedback loop between an employee's civic behavior and their perception of how their employer supports them.

Despite their observation that perceptions of organizational support ultimately lead to duties among employees to repay the organisation, the findings of Settoon, Bennett, and Liden's 1996 study did not support the notion that there is an interaction between psychological empowerment and OCB.

Lambert (2000) observed that when employees have a positive view of organizational support, they do not provide suggestions for change. Furthermore, he asserted that when an organization's support grows, employees learn to take it for granted.

Perceived organizational support was discovered to be linked to various attributes of ocb's like benevolence and compliance.

H1: Extra role behavior is strongly influenced by anticipated organizational support.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Organizational Commitment

Scholl has given several possibilities that imply a subliminal connection between OCBs and commitment (1981). When expectancy/equity needs are not met or are not functional, commitment "acts to sustain behavioral direction," according to Scholl's view. According to the model, when an employee's expectation of formal organizational rewards for their work is reduced and when their commitment to the pertinent determinant is inferred, OCBs relates to the employee's actions. Workers with a high level of loyalty are more likely to participate in OCB and less affectively devoted colleagues (Meyer & Allen, 1997). Numerous behavioral research studies have discovered a substantial link between loyalty and civic engagement

(Meyer & Allen, 1986). Organ and Ryan (1995) identified two categories of organizational citizenship behavior that have a substantial correlation with Affective commitment: altruism and compliance.

H2: Affective commitment has a strong influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

Meyer et al 1993's study indicated a negative link between continuity commitment and citizenship behavior; Shore & Wayne's 1993 study found a positive correlation. According to Moorman et al. (1993), Citizenship practises and long-term commitment have a marginally beneficial link.

H3: Organizational citizenship behavior is highly influenced by continuity commitment.

Meyer and colleagues (1993) looked into emotional and cognitive contribution in relation to citizenship behavior among registered nurses. The results showed a favourable bond among affective as well as normative contribution and civic behavior. In compared to those involving Affective commitment, the links between normative commitment and extra-role activities appear to be weaker.

H4: Normative commitment has a strong influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

Figure 1: depicts the theoretical links discussed in Hypotheses 1–9

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Survey Instrument

A drafting questionnaire was prepared to help the study achieve its goals based on careful analyses of the existing literature. There were two sections to the four-page questionnaire. Part I includes questions about the characteristics of nurses, such as their attributes (such as age, academic background, expertise, division, affiliations and salary) The second section of the questionnaire includes questions about perceived organizational support, Emotional contribution, normative contribution, continuing contribution, and OCB. The majority of the Respondents were asked to rate their responses on a 5-point Scale in the questionnaire's sections.

3.2 Pilot Study

Prior to the pilot study, research questionnaire was distributed to a group of eminent academicians and senior employees for feedback. Their suggestions were incorporated into the updated/modified questionnaire. The researcher met with 90 nurses and collected responses to the revised/modified questionnaire in the time given for the trial experiment. The survey was then pilot tested and upgraded depending on its findings. This method improved the accuracy and relevance of the questionnaire.

3.3 Population

The investigation took place in Tiruchirappalli District private hospitals with over 225 beds. Tiruchirappalli, the fourth-largest city in Tamil Nadu is located on the Cauvery River. Tiruchirappalli City Corporation is made up of 60 wards and four zonal offices named Srirangam, Ariyamangalam, Golden Rock, and Kobiabishekapuram. Tiruchirappalli City Corporation covers an area of 146.70 square kilometers. Three hospitals with a total capacity of more than 225 beds were picked, each with a staff of 647 nurses, 310 doctors, and 325 technicians, for a total workforce of 1282 people.

3.4 Sample Instrument

In statistics, a research instrument is the item or source from which a sample is obtained. The researcher decided that 648 nurses make up the sample frame for the study out of the 1282 professionals that collectively work in the three hospitals. Each hospital has 303, 160, or 185 nurses.

3.5 Sample Size

The sample size was calculated using the formula indicated below.

$(Z s/e)^2$ Cochran's random sample algorithm

Where Z is the specified alpha score of significance level in each tail, which equals 1.96;

s is the pilot study's estimated standard deviation, which equals 0.441; and

The permissible margin of error for the mean being approximated is denoted by e. (0.05)

The expected sample size for the study was 299 persons.

The final surveys were distributed to 400 nurses, and the researcher eventually obtained 299 completed questionnaires as samples. When the data gathering period has concluded, 74% of the sample population had responded.

3.6 Sampling Method

Simple random sampling was used. It is a method in which each population unit has an equal chance of being chosen (Uma Sekaran, 2001).

3.7 Analytical Approach

This analysis made use of route modelling with partial least - square (PLS-PM).

3.8 Reliability

According to Table 1, all of the constructs, including perceived organizational support, emotional commitment, normative commitment, continuation commitment, and OCB, are sufficiently reliable, with internal consistency values greater than 0.60. These are 0.879, 0.885, 0.911, 0.909, and 0.873. Last but not least, Hotelling's T-squared test results in Table 2 revealed that the mean of the five dimensions differed significantly at the 1% level.

Table 1: Reliability

Construct	Number of matters	Alpha significance
Observed organizational support	16	0.876
Affective contribution	08	0.885
Continuance contribution	08	0.911
Normative contribution	08	0.909
Extra role behavior	16	0.872

Table 2: Hoteing's T-Squared Test

Hotelling's T-Squared	F	df1	df2	Sig
109.332	27.058	4	295	.000

3.9 Convergent Validity

We used simple random sampling. Using this technique, each population unit has an equal chance of getting chosen (Uma Sekaran, 2001).

The convergent validity of each construct was assessed consuming the metric of Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which is the regular modification shared between a concept and its elements. If a construct's AVE is more than 0.5, it is regarded to take significant convergent validity. In exceptional circumstances, AVE standards of up to 0.40 and composite reliability values of up to 0.60 are measured acceptable if they are critical to the model. Chin 1995. As a result, the convergent rationality of the study constructs was validated.

Validation of Models Outcomes of the PLS-PM Building Block Equation Research Model

PLS was used to test the hypotheses since it generates beta coefficients that are similar to OLS regression coefficients. PLS was used to evaluate the routes from independent factors to

dependent variables in order to determine their direction, size, and significance in order to evaluate the study hypotheses. To assess the significance of the paths, the bootstrapping method was applied. The recommended model successfully explained 94.4 percent of the variation in organizational citizenship behavior.

Table 3: Construct Level Correlation of Research Model

Hypothesis	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (1-tailed)
H1	Observed organizational support	Organizational citizenship behavior	0.907**	0.000
H2	Affective contribution		0.875**	0.000
H4	Continuance contribution		0.621**	0.000
H3	Normative contribution		0.614**	0.000

** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (1-tailed)

The construct correlation is shown in Table 3. It reveals that there are positive relationships between POS and OCB ($r=0.907$), AC and OCB ($r=0.875$), CC and OCB ($r=0.621$), and NC and OCB ($r=0.614$).

Hypotheses results

H1: Extra role behavior is strongly influenced by anticipated organizational support.

Figure 2 shows that the connection between anticipated organizational support and Extra role behavior was significant at the 0.05 level ($\beta=0.724$, $t=9.995$). This implies that anticipated organizational support influences Extra role behavior significantly. This provided assistance to H1. (See Table 4)

Table 4: Bootstrap Summary of Research Model and Hypothesis Result

Hypothesis	Entire sample estimate	Mean of sub samples	Standard error	T- Statistic	R Square value	Result
H1	0.724	0.708	0.0724	9.9954	0.944	significant
H2	0.471	0.4791	0.0544	8.6557		significant
H3	0.005	0.0248	0.0181	0.2761		Insignificant
H4	-0.206	-0.2124	0.0395	-5.2216		Significant

H2: Affective commitment has a strong influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

Because the association between the two variables was found to be significant at the 0.05 level ($\beta=0.471$, $t= 8.656$), it can be inferred that Affective commitment has a considerable influence on organizational citizenship behavior. This provided evidence to back up H2 and the literature review. (See Table 4)

H3: Organizational citizenship behavior is highly influenced by continuity commitment.

The relation between continuity contribution and organizational citizenship behavior is not substantial at the 0.05 level ($\beta=0.005$, $t=0.2761$), suggesting that continuity commitment had no influence on OCB. H3 is hence disregarded. View Forth table

H4: Normative commitment has a strong influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

The path from NC to OCB was unfavorable and significant at the 0.05 level (beta= -0.206, t= 5.222). It assisted with both the literature review and H3. It implies impact that organizational citizenship behavior is significantly tied by normative commitment.

Table 5: Convergent Validity

Variables	AVE assessment	Composite Reliability
Observed organizational support	0.442805	0.873833
Affective contribution	0.503328	0.846076
Continuance contribution	0.448482	0.807812
Normative contribution	0.506989	0.855432
Extra role behavior	0.493512	0.882707

3.10 Demographic profile of respondents

76 percent of nurses are between the ages of 21 and 30, 89 percent have nursing diplomas, 78 percent have less than five years of experience, fifty percent of responders are staff nurses, 24 percent work in intensive care units, and 89 percent earn less than Rupees 10,000 per year.

Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Citizenship

The study's major premise was that nurses' views of organizational support would influence their attitudes towards citizenship.

Figure 2: PLS- Path Analysis of Investigation Model

According to the findings of the PLS-path analysis, there is a substantial link between observed organizational support and the results of the current evaluation supported the hypothesis of the learning. In an effort to provide a likely explanation for study findings, literature reviews are used to try and help.

Previous research has shown a substantial correlation between individual organizational citizenship behavior traits and perceived organizational support (Moorman et al., 1998; Social interchange, in the view of Organ and Konovsky (1989), is a reflection of OCB. People draw the conclusion that there is a reciprocal link between the organization and themselves if they sense they are being preserved properly. Additionally, they are less concerned with the benefits of extra-role behavior. Employees will switch from social interchange to commercial commerce if they feel they are not being treated fairly and equally by the company.

Managers also have the authority to influence employees who engage in OCB. Subordinates are more likely to display excellent citizenship if they sense they are being treated fairly. Ostroff, 1992. Supervisory trust, according to research by Podsakoff et al. (1990), modulates the linkage between extra role behavior and discussion relations.

Affective commitment and Positive Organizational Citizenship

The study's major hypothesis was that Affective commitment would influence nurses' civic behavior. The conclusions of this research validated the exploration hypothesis by illustrative that Affective commitment has a substantial influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

According to previous research (Bolon, 1997), the two key drivers of citizenship action were Affective commitment and contentment with coworkers. According to some study, people can demonstrate their affective connection to the organization by engaging in citizenship behaviors. Ricketta and Landerer achieved the same result (2002). According to their findings, Affective commitment, accountability, and OCB are all linked. The data revealed that OCB is dependent on both.

Corporate citizenship and commitment to continuity

The study anticipated that nurses' civic behavior would be influenced by their commitment to continuity. The outcomes of the PLS-path analysis display there is no meaningful relationship among ongoing commitment and extra role behavior. The research hypothesis was not supported by the outcomes of the present examination. Additionally, this conclusion was not supported by the literature review. It implies that nurses do not perceive any risk in leaving the organization. They are always prepared to break away from the group. This conclusion may be explained by the dearth of genuine rewards in hospitals, such as pay, seniority, and benefits.

Normative Commitment Behavior and Organizational Citizenship

The study proposed the premise that nurses' commitment to standards will influence their citizenship in hospitals. According to the study's findings, normative commitment has a considerable influence on organizational citizenship behavior. The current investigation's findings support the research premise.

Meyer (2002) initiate a positive association among corporate citizenship behavior as well as normative contribution in a meta-analysis study. Bolon (1993) examined two categories of OCB in relation to organizational commitment: OCBI (citizenship behaviors directed towards other people) and OCBO (organizational commitment behaviors) (citizenship behaviors that

benefited the general organization). The findings revealed that normative commitment was connected with coworker-rated OCBI but not with supervisor-rated OCBI.

4. CONCLUSION

The goal of the study is to determine how extra role behavior in Tiruchirappalli District hospitals is influenced by observed organizational support and three distinct forms of job involvement. According to the PLS path analysis, there is a significant correlation between observed organizational support and extra role behavior, as well as between Affective contribution and extra role behavior, normative contribution and extra role behavior, and continuance contribution and extra role behavior.

In order to improved comprehend the link and important causes, the study developed and assessed a structural model that combines observed organizational support, Affective contribution, continuing contribution, and normative contribution to extra role behavior. All other paths were found to be valid, excluding the one that linked ongoing commitment to corporate citizenship behavior.

The study also demonstrated that by taking the previously described variables into consideration, one may forecast hospitals' civic behavior. The findings of this study shed insight on how various types of organizational commitment and observed organizational support influence extra role behavior.

Consequences of the Research

The conclusions of this evaluation have a duty to be taken seriously by hospitals and nursing supervisors. According to this study, nurses who have an emotional connection to the company are more likely than those who do not to engage in civic behavior. However, the hospital cannot rely on effective dedication from nurses until they are aware of the facility's mission, goals, and objectives. The nurses must obtain this information from hospital administrators in a clear and concise manner.

The relationship between Affective contribution and extra role behavior reveals that nurses have deep emotional attachments to the hospitals where they work and appreciate their engagement in the community. As a result, hospital administration should recognize emotionally committed nurses and support them through recognition and prizes in order to strengthen patients' emotional attachment to hospitals. As a result, it will improve nurses' civic behavior.

The impact of normative commitment on organizational citizenship shows that nurses feel required to remain in order to carry out the institutions' objectives and mission. Hospitals should prioritize nurses who are more connected to their work or duty.

Future Directions for Research

Unfortunately, the small sample size in this study may have made it difficult to determine the relationship between the components accurately. As a result, a greater trial size might be used to replicate the current study. Private hospitals made up the study's sample, therefore

conclusions about other hospitals, especially government hospitals, might not generalize. This study might be broadened to include government hospitals because organizational policies, pay systems, and benefits vary across public and private hospitals as well as within private hospitals. The surprising outcomes of this evaluation may be attributed toward cultural alterations because the majority of prior research was carried out in Western nations. It might be useful to compare Western and Eastern nations.

Future research can be conducted at multi-cultural organizations, such as those owned or run by foreigners. Work cultures and ethics would differ between organizations.

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